

Synthesis of iron(III)-humic substances complexes of different lipophilicity profile with a use of alcohol precipitation

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Keywords: Humic substances, Fe(III) complexes, alcohol precipitation, lipophilicity; tritium labeling
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17341475

Humic substances (HS) are supramolecular macroligands rich in functional groups that complex metal ions, enabling sustainable and biomedical applications, including iron formulations for treating iron deficiency anemia and plant chlorosis. Its hydrophilic-lipophilic balance governs membrane transport and bioavailability, tritium labeling permits molecular-level evaluation of HS behavior and lipophilicity. The aim of this work was to obtain Fe(III) complexes with humic macroligands possessing different lipophilicity profiles and to determine the effect of the alcohol precipitation on the properties of the preparations.

Sodium humate from leonardite (Powhumus 85%, Humintech Ltd, Germany) was used as a HS. The tritium label was introduced into HS by the method of thermal activation of tritium. Anhydrous FeCl₃ (UD-Bio, China) served as the iron precursor. The synthesis was carried out in two stages: precipitation of Fe(OH)₃ at 7-10 °C and pH = 7, and addition of the resulting precipitate to HS at 60 °C in an alkaline medium (pH = 11), followed by acidification to pH = 6.5. The resulting preparations were subjected to multiple alcohol precipitation with ethanol with an increasing proportion of the organic phase (30 – 70 %). A control sample was obtained without alcohol precipitation. 7 samples were obtained in total. Lipophilicity was determined by the octanol-water partition coefficient (K_{ow}) using liquid scintillation spectrometry, and particle core sizes was determined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and the hydrodynamic radius was determined by dynamic light scattering (DLS). Lipophilicity was assessed in two series: with pre-centrifugation (removal of the solid phase) and without. Centrifugation before alcohol precipitation decreased lipophilicity (K_{ow} = 0.11 - 0.24), whereas increasing the ethanol content in the non-centrifuged series raised K_{ow} to 0.63 - 0.65; the control samples showed moderate lipophilicity (K_{ow} = 0.27 - 0.40). Concomitantly, water solubility increased from 57 g/L in the control to 120 - 145 g/L in precipitated samples. These results indicate that alcohol precipitation drives the solubility gain irrespective of pre-centrifugation, while the pre-centrifugation step primarily modulates lipophilicity-lowering K_{ow} when applied, and yielding higher K_{ow} when omitted-thus providing a handle to tune the hydrophilic-lipophilic balance. According to TEM, the iron-oxide core size decreased from 6 nm to 1 - 3 nm after precipitation. DLS showed that the hydrodynamic radius of precipitated samples increased with ethanol content from 24.3 ± 4.0 nm to 38.4 ± 3.6 nm. The control sample exhibited the largest mean hydrodynamic radius (60.7 ± 6.2 nm). Alcohol precipitation yields Fe(III) - HS nanoparticles with smaller inorganic cores and more compact, less polydisperse hydrodynamic ensembles than the non-precipitated control.

Thus, the method makes it possible to regulate the key characteristics of Fe(III) - HS complexes: lipophilicity, solubility, and particle size. Controlling these parameters at the synthesis stage opens up opportunities for the development of effective and safe iron-based preparations.

Acknowledgements. The work was carried out within the framework of the State Task 122040600057-3.